

Effect sizes: P_Area_log

Effect sizes: D_2_Core

Effect sizes: Canopy

Effect sizes: D_2_PA

Effect sizes: HMI

Effect sizes: VNL_2

Effect sizes: Elev

Effect sizes: NPP

Effect sizes: Precip

